

Appointment Procedure of Election Commission in India : An Analysis

Paper Id : 19836 Submission Date : 2025-06-02 Acceptance Date : 2025-06-21 Publication Date : 2025-06-25

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17052797

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Abstract

The Election Commission of India occupies a pivotal position in sustaining the democratic framework of the country by ensuring free and fair elections. However, the procedure of appointment of the Chief Election Commissioner and other Election Commissioners has remained a subject of constitutional, judicial, and academic debate. The present research paper critically analyses the existing appointment process under Article 324 of the Constitution of India. It examines the historical evolution of this provision, judicial pronouncements including recent Supreme Court interventions, and the concerns of transparency, neutrality, and independence in the functioning of the ECI. The paper argues that the concentration of appointment power in the executive by Chief Election Commissioner and Other Election Commissioners (Appointment, Conditions of Service and Term of Office) Act, 2023 need to examine critically for the integrity and fairness of the institution. Through this analysis, the research seeks to contribute to the discourse on democratic accountability and institutional safeguards in India's constitutional design.

Keywords

Appointment, Constitution, Democracy, Election Commission, Fairness,

Introduction

In India, one of the most heterogeneous societies in the world, politics remains highly contentious. Both the democratic system and the state secure their legitimacy through regular free and fair elections. The ECI is responsible for India's long-standing record of uncontested, free and fair elections.[1] However, institutional development of ECI has long standing history since colonial regime. The Election Commission of India (ECI) is one of the most powerful electoral regulatory bodies in the world and one of the most widely celebrated and trusted public institutions in India.[2] The Election Commission of India was established on 25 January 1950 under Article 324[3] of the Constitution, which vested the power of appointment of the Chief Election Commissioner and other Election Commissioners in the President of India, subject to any law made by Parliament. However, since no such law was enacted for decades, appointments remained within the exclusive domain of the executive, with the President acting on the advice of the Council of Ministers. Initially, from 1950 to 1989, the Commission functioned as a single-member body headed only by the CEC, until it was briefly expanded to a three-member body in 1989, reverted in 1990, and finally established as a permanent three-member Commission in 1993. While the ECI enjoys some formal autonomy from the executive, it is not an independent agency. The executive controls the EC's finances and personnel appointments.[4] Throughout this period, the appointment procedure continued to lack transparency or consultation with opposition parties or other constitutional authorities. Article 327 of the constitution empower parliament to make legislation on elections.[5] Furthermore, article 329 Bar to interference by courts in electoral matters.[6] But judicial decisions on electoral reforms have long history in India. Judicial interventions highlighted this gap, most notably in *Anoop Baranwal v. Union of India*,[7] where the Supreme Court directed that, until Parliament enacted a law, appointments would be made by a committee consisting of the Prime Minister, the Leader of Opposition in the Lok Sabha, and the Chief Justice of India. In response, Parliament passed a law[8] which created a new selection committee comprising the Prime Minister, the Leader of Opposition, and a Union Cabinet Minister nominated by the Prime Minister. While this marked the first legislative framework for such appointments, it has been criticized for restoring executive dominance by excluding the judiciary from the process, thereby keeping the debate on ensuring transparency, independence, and neutrality in the appointment of the ECI alive.

Objective of study

The paper argues that the concentration of appointment power in the executive by Chief Election Commissioner and Other Election Commissioners (Appointment, Conditions of Service and Term of Office) Act, 2023 need to examine critically for the integrity and fairness of the institution. Through this analysis, the research seeks to contribute to the discourse on democratic accountability and institutional safeguards in India's constitutional design.

Review of Literature

Constituent assembly debates

During the Constituent Assembly debates on Article 289 of the Draft Constitution (later Article 324), members were deeply concerned with designing a mechanism that would guarantee free and fair elections. Dr. B.R. Ambedkar, introducing the provision, observed: "The House will see that the whole of the election machinery should be in the hands of a

Central Election Commission, which alone will be entitled to issue directives to returning officers, polling officers and others.”[9] He stressed that independence would come not only from the mode of appointment but also from safeguards such as tenure and removal only through impeachment-like proceedings. Several members, however, expressed apprehension that vesting appointment power solely in the executive might compromise impartiality. K.T. Shah argued: “So important a function and so vital a function should not be left to the sweet will of the executive of the day... The appointment should be made with the concurrence of at least two-thirds majority of Parliament.”[10] Similarly, Shibban Lal Saxena warned that unless the Commission was insulated from the ruling party, “the democracy we are trying to build will be put in peril by partisan appointments.” Ambedkar, responding to these concerns, defended the Drafting Committee’s position: “There is no doubt that the Chief Election Commissioner must be a person who is above all suspicion... The provision is that the President shall make the appointment, but Parliament may, by law, provide otherwise. We are leaving it open for Parliament to evolve conventions.”[11] He also noted that the security of tenure and removal procedure equating the CEC with a Supreme Court judge was itself a safeguard against executive interference. The Assembly eventually adopted Ambedkar’s draft, thus creating an independent constitutional body but leaving the appointment procedure undefined, with the expectation that Parliament would later legislate on the subject. This compromise reflected a balance between administrative practicality and institutional independence, though as later history and judicial pronouncements show, the omission has remained a contested issue in Indian democracy.

Main Text**Provision of Multi members election commission and their powers**

Under Article 324[12] of the Indian Constitution, the superintendence, direction and control of elections are vested in the Election Commission of India, which was originally a single-member body headed by the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC). However, Article 324(2)[13] empowers the President to appoint additional Election Commissioners, thereby making it a multi-member body. From 1950 to 1989, the Commission functioned with only the CEC, but in 1989 two Election Commissioners were added, withdrawn in 1990, and since 1993 it has been a permanent three-member body comprising one CEC and two Election Commissioners. All members enjoy equal powers and status, and decisions are taken collectively, with the majority prevailing in case of disagreement. The multi-member Commission exercises wide powers, including supervising elections to Parliament, State Legislatures, and the offices of President and Vice-President; preparing and revising electoral rolls; enforcing the Model Code of Conduct; recognizing political parties and allotting symbols; and advising on disqualifications of members. It also performs quasi-judicial and administrative functions under the Representation of the People Acts, 1950 and 1951.[14] Thus, the provision of a multi-member Election Commission ensures collective decision-making and strengthens the independence and neutrality of the institution in conducting free and fair elections in India.

Supreme court on Appointment of election commission

The Constitution, under Article 324(2),[15] provides that the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) and other Election Commissioners shall be appointed by the President, subject to any law made by Parliament. However, since Parliament has not enacted a specific law on the matter, the appointments have traditionally been made by the executive (the Union Government). This long-standing practice raised concerns regarding the independence of the Election Commission, given its crucial role in ensuring free and fair elections. In *Anoop Baranwal v. Union of India*,[16] the Supreme Court delivered a landmark judgment addressing this issue. The Court held that until Parliament enacts a law under Article 324(2),[17] the appointment of the CEC and Election Commissioners shall be made by the President on the advice of a committee consisting of the Prime Minister, the Leader of the Opposition (or leader of the largest opposition party) in the Lok Sabha, and the Chief Justice of India (CJI). This ruling was aimed at insulating the Election Commission from executive dominance and ensuring its institutional independence. The Court emphasized that a fair and impartial Election Commission is part of the basic structure of the Constitution, as free and fair elections are integral to democracy. It also criticized the existing practice of appointments solely on the recommendation of the executive as being contrary to constitutional values.

Law made by parliament for Appointment of EC

Parliament has now enacted a law under Article 324(2)[18] called the Chief Election Commissioner and Other Election Commissioners (Appointment, Conditions of Service and Term of Office) Act, 2023,[19] which came into force in January 2024. This Act provides that the Chief Election Commissioner (CEC) and other Election Commissioners (ECs) shall be appointed by the President on the recommendation of a selection committee consisting of the Prime Minister, the Leader of Opposition (or leader of the largest opposition party) in the Lok Sabha, and a Union Cabinet Minister nominated by the Prime Minister, thereby replacing the earlier Supreme Court-mandated collegium that included the Chief Justice of India. The Act further specifies that the CEC and ECs will have service conditions and salaries equivalent to those of the Cabinet Secretary, instead of being on par with judges of the Supreme Court as provided under the 1991 Act, and also bars their reappointment. While the law fills the constitutional vacuum envisaged under Article 324(2),[20] it has been widely criticized for tilting the balance of

power towards the executive and potentially undermining the independence of the Election Commission, a body vital for ensuring free and fair elections in India.

Conclusion

Famous cases related to the Election Commission of India have sought to establish it as an impartial and integrated institution. In *S.S. Dhanoa v. Union of India and Others*,^[21] the Supreme Court clearly signalled that nobody can be above the institution they are meant to serve, as its officers are merely creations of the institution and can exist only so long as the institution itself exists. The Court further explained in the *T.N. Seshan case*^[22] that holders of constitutional offices are expected to discharge their duties cautiously and harmoniously, in keeping with the letter and spirit of the Constitution. *The Anoop Baranwal case*^[23] marked a further step towards reforming the appointment process of the Chief Election Commissioner and other Election Commissioners to strengthen the institution. However, the Chief Election Commissioner and Other Election Commissioners (Appointment, Conditions of Service and Term of Office) Act, 2023^[24] reinforced the Union Government's dominance in the matter of appointments, including that of the Chief Election Commissioner. To truly strengthen democracy and ensure the impartiality and fairness of elections, the present law governing the appointment of Election Commissioners requires reform.

References

[1] Arjen Boin, Lauren A. Fahy, et.al. (eds), *Guardians of Public Value: How Public Organisations Become and Remain Institutions* 38 (Palgrave Macmillan, Switzerland, 2021).

[2] *Ibid* 37.

[3] *Superintendence, direction and control of elections to be vested in an Election Commission: (1) The superintendence, direction and control of the preparation of the electoral rolls for, and the conduct of, all elections to Parliament and to the Legislature of every State and of elections to the offices of President and Vice-President held under this Constitution shall be vested in a Commission (referred to in this Constitution as the Election Commission).*

(2) The Election Commission shall consist of the Chief Election Commissioner and such number of other Election Commissioners, if any, as the President may from time-to-time fix and the appointment of the Chief Election Commissioner and other Election Commissioners shall, subject to the provisions of any law made in that behalf by Parliament, be made by the President.

(3) When any other Election Commissioner is so appointed the Chief Election Commissioner shall act as the Chairman of the Election Commission.

(4) Before each general election to the House of the People and to the Legislative Assembly of each State, and before the first general election and thereafter before each biennial election to the Legislative Council of each State having such Council, the President may also appoint after consultation with the Election Commission such Regional Commissioners as he may consider necessary to assist the Election Commission in the performance of the functions conferred on the Commission by clause (1).

(5) Subject to the provisions of any law made by Parliament, the conditions of service and tenure of office of the Election Commissioners and the Regional Commissioners shall be such as the President may by rule determine: Provided that the Chief Election Commissioner shall not be removed from his office except in like manner and on the like grounds as a Judge of the Supreme Court and the conditions of service of the Chief Election Commissioner shall not be varied to his disadvantage after his appointment: Provided further that any other Election Commissioner or a Regional Commissioner shall not be removed from office except on the recommendation of the Chief Election Commissioner.

(6) The President, or the Governor of a State, shall, when so requested by the Election Commission, make available to the Election Commission or to a Regional Commissioner such staff as may be necessary for the discharge of the functions conferred on the Election Commission by clause (1). Constitution of India, art. 324.

[4] *Supra* note 1 page 41.

[5] *Power of Parliament to make provision with respect to elections to Legislatures: Subject to the provisions of this Constitution, Parliament may from time to time by law make provision with respect to all matters relating to, or in Connection with, elections to either House of Parliament or to the House or either House of the Legislature of a State including the preparation of electoral rolls, the delimitation of constituencies and all other matters necessary for securing the due constitution of such House or Houses. Constitution of India, art. 327.*

[6] *Bar to interference by courts in electoral matters: Notwithstanding anything in this Constitution (a) the validity of any law relating to the delimitation of constituencies or the allotment of seats to such constituencies, made or purporting to be made under article 327 or article 328, shall not be called in question in any court; (b) no election to either House of Parliament or to the House or either House of the Legislature of a State shall be called in question except by an election petition presented to such authority and in such manner as may be provided for by or under any law made by the appropriate Legislature. Constitution of India, art. 329.*

[7] 2023 (6) SCC 1.

- [8] *The Election Commission (Appointment, Conditions of Service and Term of Office) Act, 2023, Act 49 of 2023.*
- [9] *Constituent Assembly Debates, available at <https://indiankanoon.org/doc/1155224/> (Last visited on February, 2025).*
- [10] *Ibid*
- [11] *Ibid.*
- [12] *Supra note 3.*
- [13] *Ibid.*
- [14] *The Representation of the People Acts, 1950 and 1951, (Act 43 of 1950 and 1951).*
- [15] *Supra note 3.*
- [16] *Supra note 7.*
- [17] *Supra note 3.*
- [18] *Ibid.*
- [19] *Supra note 8.*
- [20] *Supra note 3.*
- [21] *S.S. Dhanoa v. Union of India, (1991) 3 S.C.C. 584.*
- [22] *T.N. Seshan, Chief Election commissioner of India v. Union of India, (1995) 4 S.C.C. 611.*
- [23] *Supra note 7.*
- [24] *Supra note 8.*